

第3讲 CiteSpace 下载与安装

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李杰科学网博客: <http://blog.sciencenet.cn/u/jerrycueb>

开放科学计量学学习平台: <https://www.metamatrix.cn/home>

The longer you can look back, the farther you can look forward (回顾历史越久远, 展望未来就越深远)。

CiteSpace软件下载与安装说明

*CiteSpace是基于Java开发的科学计量数据可视化工具，因此在下载和使用CiteSpace之前，用户需要在自己的电脑上安装JAVA。

对于新版的CiteSpace而言，其已经集成了JAVA，因为只需要安装CiteSpace即可，不再需要单独再安装JAVA。

Java SE Development Kit 17.0.3.1		
This software is licensed under the Oracle No-Fee Terms and Conditions License.		
Product / File Description	File Size	Download
Linux Arm 64 Compressed Archive	171.6 MB	https://download.oracle.com/java/17/archive/jdk-17.0.3.1_linux-aarch64_bin.tar.gz (sha256)
Linux Arm 64 RPM Package	153.61 MB	https://download.oracle.com/java/17/archive/jdk-17.0.3.1_linux-aarch64_bin.rpm (sha256)
Linux x64 Compressed Archive	172.81 MB	https://download.oracle.com/java/17/archive/jdk-17.0.3.1_linux-x64_bin.tar.gz (sha256)
Linux x64 Debian Package	148.35 MB	https://download.oracle.com/java/17/archive/jdk-17.0.3.1_linux-x64_bin.deb (sha256)
Linux x64 RPM Package	155.22 MB	https://download.oracle.com/java/17/archive/jdk-17.0.3.1_linux-x64_bin.rpm (sha256)
macOS Arm 64 Compressed Archive	167.42 MB	https://download.oracle.com/java/17/archive/jdk-17.0.3.1_macos-aarch64_bin.tar.gz (sha256)
macOS Arm 64 DMG Installer	166.82 MB	https://download.oracle.com/java/17/archive/jdk-17.0.3.1_macos-aarch64_bin.dmg (sha256)
macOS x64 Compressed Archive	169.96 MB	https://download.oracle.com/java/17/archive/jdk-17.0.3.1_macos-x64_bin.tar.gz (sha256)
macOS x64 DMG Installer	169.37 MB	https://download.oracle.com/java/17/archive/jdk-17.0.3.1_macos-x64_bin.dmg (sha256)
Windows x64 Compressed Archive	171.62 MB	https://download.oracle.com/java/17/archive/jdk-17.0.3.1_windows-x64_bin.zip (sha256)
Windows x64 Installer	152.65 MB	https://download.oracle.com/java/17/archive/jdk-17.0.3.1_windows-x64_bin.exe (sha256)
Windows x64 msi Installer	151.53 MB	https://download.oracle.com/java/17/archive/jdk-17.0.3.1_windows-x64_bin.msi (sha256)

下载地址：<https://www.oracle.com/java/technologies/javase/jdk17-archive-downloads.html>

CiteSpace软件

CiteSpace目前有3个版本，分别为Basic版、Standard版以及Advanced版本。Basic具备了基础的科学计量与知识图谱分析功能，免费向所有人使用。Standard和Advanced版本为收费版，可以提供更加多样的用户需求与设置。对于初学者而言Basic版本足够满足其进行数据分析学习的需求，然而对于要使用CiteSpace进行论文或报告撰写的用户来讲，建议使用Standard或Advanced版本。

CiteSpace下载地址：<https://citespace.podia.com/>

类别	功能	Basic版	Standard版	Advanced版
功能许可	有效期	1年	1年	2年
	可用计算机数量	不限制	1	2
	网络最大规模	300	100,000	100,000
	最大时间跨度	30	120	120
功能集成	GPT 聚类标签的生成		+	+
	Dimensions (API)		+	+
	Semantic Scholar (API)		+	+
数据源	Web of Science	+	+	+
	Scopus	+	+	+
	Dimensions	+	+	+
	CSSCI	+	+	+
	CNKI	+	+	+
	CSV Importer (Generic)		+	+
	MySQL		+	+
	Pubmed		+	+
	聚类视图 (Cluster View)	+	+	+
	双图叠加 (Dual-Map Overlays)	+	+	+
可视化	时间线视图 (Timeline View)	+	+	+
	节点的3D效果 (3D Effect)		+	+
	地理可视化 (Geographic Map)		+	+
	圆形视图 (Circular View)		+	+
	山峦图 (Landscape View)		+	+
	SVG视图		+	+
	时区图 (Timezone View)		+	+
	作者合作网络分析	+	+	+
分析功能	关键词共词分析	+	+	+
	文献共被引分析	+	+	+
	引文级联分析		+	+
	概念树 (Concept Trees)		+	+
	术语共现分析		+	+
	结构变异分析		+	+
	文本处理 (Text Processing)		+	+
附加功能	不确定性分析 (Uncertainty Analysis)		+	+
	报告生成 (Summary Report)	+	+	+
	视频录制 (Video Recording)		+	+

Products

My products
More products

1. CiteSpace Basic (Free)

📄 15 files

2. CiteSpace (Standard)

📄 10 files

3. CiteSpace (Advanced)

📄 32 files

CiteSpace下载地址: <https://citespace.podia.com/>

CiteSpace版本说明

CiteSpace Blogs Exemplars Gallery FAQs Standard Advanced Products

Glossary Videos References

Products / Download

3. CiteSpace (Advanced)

32 files • 2.82 GB

[Download](#)

6.4.R1 Advanced for Windows (Built 12/27/2024; Expires 12/31/2026)
Timeline labels fixed.

[下载Citespace](#)

CiteSpace-6.4.1-installer.exe • 36.7 MB

6.3.R3 Advanced (Built 6/27/2024; Expires 12/31/2025)

- New Colormaps
- Ollama: Updated: llama3, gemma:2b
- GPT: gpt-4o as the default model
- Scopus: References: Revised with an increased accuracy
- Google Earth KML Generator (Version 2.3)
- Timeline View: Cluster Labels: Fixed

CiteSpace-6.4.1-installer.exe为安装包，用户双击后，按照提示安装即可。

CiteSpace安装

MAC上安装CiteSpace

CiteSpace安装

双击打开

注意：首次打开后，软件需要联网，并在联网的状态下完成数据和功能的配置。

1

名称	修改日期	类型	大小
CiteSpace-6.4.1-installer.exe	2024/12/30 9:09	应用程序	37,604 KB

双击

2

3

CiteSpace配置后自动打开

CiteSpace: Welcome!

CiteSpace (c) 2003-2024 Chaomei Chen. All rights reserved. English

[6.4.R1 Demo Video](#) * [CiteSpace Survey](#) * [CiteSpace Blogs](#)

Current Versions: 6.4.R1, 6.3.R3, 6.3.R1 (Advanced)

[CiteSpace101 \(Experimental GPT\)](#) | [CiteSpace FAQ in English/Chinese \(英文/中文\)](#)

Videos: (1) [Visual Analytic Studies of Science \(2024\)](#) (2) [研究领域的形成, 发展, 和消亡 \(2022\)](#) (3) [Delineating the Scholarly Landscape of a Research Field \(2021\)](#)

[Upgrade to CiteSpace \(Advanced\): 1 Year on 1 Computer; 2 Years on 2 Computers](#)

升级高级版: 微信/支付宝 (S/¥) : 1年1台电脑; 2年2台电脑

注意: CiteSpace的官网为 citespace.podia.com。任何其它网站均未经授权。

Warning: The citespace.podia.com is the official website of CiteSpace. CiteSpace distributed on any other websites are unauthorized.

System Information

CiteSpace 6.4.R1 (64-bit) Advanced	Windows 11 (null/null)	Java 22.0.2+11 (64-bit)
Built: December 27, 2024	Processors: 16	Substrate VM
Expire: December 31, 2026	Host: 67VGMJ3 159.226.100.236	Java Home: null

Key Publications

- Chen, C. (2020) [A Glimpse of the First Eight Months of the COVID-19 Literature on Microsoft Academic Graph](#). Front. Res. Metr. Anal. 5:607286.
- Chen, C., Song, M. (2019) [Visualizing a field of research: A methodology of systematic scientometric reviews](#). PLoS ONE, 14(10):e0223994.
- Chen, C. (2017) [Science mapping: A systematic review of the literature](#). JDIS, 2(2), 1-40.
- Chen, C. (2016) [CiteSpace: A Practical Guide for Mapping Scientific Literature](#). Nova Science Publishers.
- Chen, C. et al. (2010) [The structure and dynamics of co-citation clusters: A multiple-perspective co-citation analysis](#). JASIST, 61(7), 1386-1409.
- Chen, C. (2006) [CiteSpace II: Detecting and visualizing emerging trends and transient patterns in scientific literature](#). JASIST, 57(3), 359-377.
- Chen, C. (2004) [Searching for intellectual turning points: Progressive Knowledge Domain Visualization](#). Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., 101(Suppl.), 5303-5310.
- Chen, C. (2010) [System and method for automatically generating systematic reviews of a scientific field](#). US Patent US20110295903A1.

Acknowledgements

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点击Agree打开Citespace

This version of CiteSpace is for personal use only. Use it at your own risk.

点击Agree后，进入功能参数区。

The screenshot displays the CiteSpace 6.4.R1 (64-bit) Advanced interface. The window title is "CiteSpace 6.4.R1 (64-bit) Advanced - (c) 2003-2024 Chaomei Chen - Home: C:\Users\metascience". The menu bar includes File, Projects, Data, Visualization, Geographical, Overlay Maps, Analytics, Network, Text, Preferences, Tutorials, and Help.

The main interface is divided into several sections:

- Web of Science:** Contains a "Projects" section with a "New" button and a dropdown menu showing "Demo 1: Terrorism (1996-2003)". Below this are fields for "Project Home", "Data Directory", and "Configuration" (Source=WoS; LRF=2.5; L/N=10; LBY=5; e=1.0). A "Start" button is highlighted in green, along with "Stop" and "Reset" buttons. A "JVM Memory" section shows "12887 (MB) Used" and "0 %".
- Time Slicing:** Includes a "Time Slicing" section with "From" (1996), "To" (2003), and "#Years Per Slice" (1) dropdown menus.
- Text Processing:** Includes a "Text Processing" section with "Term Source" (Title, Abstract, Author Keywords (DE), Keywords Plus (ID)) and "Term Type" (Noun Phrases, Burst Terms, Detect Bursts, Entropy) options.
- Node Types:** Includes a "Node Types" section with radio buttons for Author, Institution, Country, Keyword, Term, Source, Category, Reference (selected), Cited Author, and Cited Journal.
- Links:** Includes a "Links" section with "Strength" (Cosine) and "Scope" (Within Slices) dropdown menus.
- Selection Criteria:** Includes a "Selection Criteria" section with tabs for g-index (selected), Top N, Top N%, Thresholds, Citations, Usage180, and Usage2013. A text box explains the selection method: "The selection uses a modified g-index in each slice: $g^2 \leq k \sum_{i \leq g} c_i, k \in Z^+$ ". Below this, a text box says "To include more or fewer nodes, increase or decrease the scale factor k = 25".
- Pruning and Visualization:** Includes a "Pruning" section with tabs for Pruning and Visualization. The Pruning section has checkboxes for Pathfinder, Minimum Spanning Tree, Pruning sliced networks, and Pruning the merged network.

首次使用CiteSpace, 那么点击Start尝试对案例数据的可视化。

CiteSpace 6.4.R1 (64-bit) Advanced - (c) 2003-2024 Chaomei Chen - Home: C:\Users\metascience

File Projects Data Visualization Geographical Overlay Maps Analytics Network Text Preferences Tutorials Help

Web of Science

Projects

New Demo 1: Terrorism (1996-2003) More Actions ...

Project Home: c:\citespace\Examples\WoS\Terrorism1990-2003\project

Data Directory: c:\citespace\Examples\WoS\Terrorism1990-2003\data

Configuration: Source=WoS; LRF=2.5; L/N=10; LB=5; e=1.0

Start Stop Reset JVM Memory 12887 (MB) Used 0 %

Space Status

1-year slices	criteria	space	nodes	links / all
Pruning configuration:				
1996	g=30, k=25	405	30	28 / 28
1997	g=41, k=25	561	41	87 / 87
1998	g=29, k=25	487	29	36 / 36
1999	g=54, k=25	766	54	135 / 243
2000	g=45, k=25	1025	45	112 / 195
2001	g=76, k=25	1590	76	190 / 768
2002	g=100, k=25	4986	100	250 / 967
2003	g=94, k=25	5064	94	235 / 426

Process Reports

Document Types
1513 Article

Distinct references [Valid]: 27660 95.5110%
Distinct references [Invalid]: 1300 4.4890%

Parsing Time: 1.216 seconds
Total Run time: 1.657 seconds

Merged network: Nodes=375, Links=1042
Exclusion List: 0
Network modeling ends at Mon Dec 30 09:25:24 CST 2024.

Time Slicing

From 1996 JAN To 2003 DEC #Years Per Slice 1

Text Processing

Term Source

Title Abstract Author Keywords (DE) Keywords Plus (ID)

Term Type

Noun Phrases Burst Terms Detect Bursts Entropy

Node Types

Author Institution Country Keyword Term Source Category

Reference Cited Author Cited Journal

Links

Strength Cosine Scope Within Slices

Selection Criteria

g-index Top N Top N% Thresholds Citations Usage180 Usage2013

The selection uses a modified g-index in each slice: $g^2 \leq k \sum_{i \leq g} c_i, k \in \mathbb{Z}^+$

To include more or fewer nodes, increase or decrease the scale factor k = 25

Pruning Visualization

Pruning

Pathfinder Pruning sliced networks
 Minimum Spanning Tree Pruning the merged network

Your Options

? Project Title: Demo 1: Terrorism (1996-2003)

Time Frame: 1996-2003
Qualified Records: 1513

How do you like to proceed?

Visualize Save As GraphML Cancel

在对CiteSpace的可视化调整后，将调整后的结果可以点击保存。

Visible	Count	Centra...	Year	Cited References
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	38	0.01	2001	SCHUSTER MA, 2001, NE...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	33	0.04	1997	FRANZ DR, 1997, JAMA-J ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	31	0.02	2002	GALEA S, 2002, NEW EN...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	30	0.10	1999	INGLESBY TV, 1999, JAMA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	29	0.17	1999	HENDERSON DA, 1999, J...
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<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	26	0.03	1997	TOROK TJ, 1997, JAMA-J ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	21	0.01	1999	NORTH CS, 1999, JAMA-J ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	17	0.04	1997	CHRISTOPHER GW, 1997...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	17	0.00	1998	HOFFMAN B, 1998, INSID...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	15	0.01	1997	TUCKER JB, 1997, JAMA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	15	0.01	1997	SIMON JD, 1997, JAMA-J A...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	15	0.00	2002	SCHLENGER WE, 2002, J...
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<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.03	2000	MACINTYRE AG, 2000, JA...
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<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	5	0.01	1998	HENDERSON DA, 1998, E...

Control Panel

Colormap | Burstness | Search | Clusters

Labels | Layout | Views

Keyword | Term | Overlay Labels

By Degree Show Frequency

Threshold: 10

Font Size: 5

Node Size: 1

Node Labels

By Cluster Show Frequency

Threshold: 2

Font Size: 5

Node Size: 17

Link Labels

Show Link Labels Show Link Strengths

Font Size: 8

Cluster Labels

Threshold: 0

Font Size: 16

Show Cluster Labels Over Time

Max Length: 150

Minimizing Overlaps

Cluster Labels Node Labels

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<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	17	0.00	1998	HOFFMAN B, 1998, INSID...
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<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	11	0.01	1999	KEIM M, 1999, ANN EMER...
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*AM PSYCH ASS (1994)

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Visible	Count	Centra...	Year	Cited References
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